

**INFORMAL WASTE WORKERS IN PLASTIC WASTE MANAGEMENT: THEIR
STATUS, CHALLENGES, AND CONTRIBUTION IN LALIPUR METROPOLITAN
CITY**

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List of Abbreviations

ADB: Asian Development Bank

CSO: Civil Society Organization

EU: European Union

HDPE: High-Density Polyethylene

ILO: International Labor Organization

IWWs: Informal Waste Workers

KMC: Kathmandu Metropolitan City

LDPE: Low-Density Polyethylene

LMC: Lalitpur Metropolitan City

MSW: Municipal Solid Waste

PET: Polyethylene Terephthalate

PP: Polypropylene

PPE: Personal Protective Equipment

PRISM: Poverty Reduction of Informal Waste Workers and Waste Management Sector Project

SSF: Social Security Fund

SWM: Solid Waste Management

UNDP: United Nations Development Programme

UNEP: United Nations Environment Programme

Abstract

Kathmandu Valley, including Lalitpur Metropolitan City (LMC), faces severe challenges in plastic waste management due to rapid urbanization and increasing plastic consumption. While formal waste management systems focus on collection and disposal, informal waste workers (IWWs) bridge the gap by collecting wastes from peripheral areas that are beyond municipal limits.

This study aims to assess the socio-economic conditions, occupational hazards, and gender disparities among IWWs in LMC. A mixed-method approach was employed, combining surveys with 66 informal waste workers and key informant interviews with scrap center owners and municipal official.

Findings reveal that IWWs collect and segregate an average of 60–70 kg of plastic waste daily, significantly reducing landfill waste and supporting recycling industries. Despite their contributions, they work under hazardous conditions, lacking safety gear, health services, and financial security. Women in waste management face additional challenges, including lower wages, limited mobility, and poor menstrual hygiene facilities. The informal nature of their work results in job insecurity, income fluctuations, and vulnerability to exploitation.

To build inclusive and sustainable waste management practices, it is crucial to integrate and recognize IWWs into the formal system. Supporting them with legal protection, fair wages, access to health services, and financial security can improve their socio-economic condition while boosting the recycling sector. Collaboration among policymakers, municipal authorities, and the private sector is necessary to ensure that IWWs receive resources and security, ultimately enhancing plastic waste recovery and contributing to the circular economy.

Keywords: Informal waste workers (IWWs), Socio-economic challenges, Gender Disparities, Plastic Waste Management, Circular Economy

Chapter 1 : Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

Kathmandu Valley is one of the fastest-growing cities in South Asia with the rapid expansion of urbanization and industrialization. This growth has led to an increase in the production of solid waste, with Kathmandu Valley producing over 1200 metric tons of waste every day (Kathmandu Post, 2024). Since the city mostly relies on sweeping, collecting, and dumping waste in landfills, managing waste has become one of the ongoing issues (Sapkota et al., 2020). In Nepal, civil society organizations (CSOs), waste management companies, and municipalities are responsible for managing household solid waste. However, these entities often neglect waste dumped in river banks and roadsides, which are managed by informal sectors such as waste pickers, cycle hawkers etc. They are also termed informal waste workers (IWWs). The major concerns of formal waste management rely only on the collection and transfer of waste, while the IWWs operate in between these processes.

The term "informal sector" refers to a broad range of activities that take place outside of the formal economy, both legal and illegal. It includes a variety of businesses that are generally characterized by inadequate pay, minimal work security, and no legal protection (Aguilar & Campuzano, 2009). An individual who collects recyclable and reusable materials outside of the official economy without a contract or social benefits is known as an informal waste worker. They are either self-employed or affiliated with small, unregulated networks involved in sorting, collection, and selling of waste materials gathered from streets, residential neighborhoods, riverbanks, and landfills. There are several ways to identify or classify IWWs, including waste pickers, sanitation workers, bicycle hawkers, door-to-door waste collectors, and others. Despite their different tasks, they all have an integral role in the waste management sector. Their primary responsibility is to collect waste from the environment, categorize them into materials with high resale value, and sell it to scrap centers, locally known as *Kawadi Center*, so that it can be recycled or reused (Karmacharya, 2022).

IWWs contribute significantly to diverting waste from landfills by collecting and selling recyclable waste to scrap centers (Khanal& Ojha, 2023). Even though IWWs role in the waste management sector is crucial, they are among the most insecure jobs, with no enforcement of national minimum wages or working hours. The informal waste business is active, with a huge number of workers involved for a long time, yet they are neither supported nor recognized (Reuters, 2024). IWWs work outside of the official system, in hazardous situations, for inadequate wages, and often without any protection from national laws (Kunwar & Singh, 2021). IWWs promote the circular economy, which has long-term environmental benefits, and reduce landfill waste through recycling efforts. Regardless, they work in uncertain situations with little negotiating leverage and unfavorable market circumstances (World Bank, 2024). The majority of workers have challenging living conditions as they belong to low socioeconomic backgrounds. They constantly encounter potentially hazardous situations that threaten their safety but are unaware of occupational health and safety (UNDP, 2023).

IWWs operate without direct supervision or formal employer-employee relationships with recycling companies or scrap dealers. The majority rely on daily wages with traders without fixed selling points. The income instability makes them struggle to provide for their families and maintain their livelihoods by gathering recyclables from waste (Karmacharya, 2022). Women in waste management balance both household responsibilities and work, yet they are frequently disregarded, performing low-paying tasks (UNEP, 2022). This study examines socioeconomic challenges, hazardous working conditions, lack of formal recognition, and disparities among waste workers. The challenges of limited access to occupational safety and fair payment and division in roles and responsibilities are highlighted. This study emphasizes the importance of IWWs in diverting waste from landfills and their undervalued contributions to plastic waste management and the circular economy.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

In Lalitpur Metropolitan City, the total generation of municipal wastes in 2011 was 84.5 MT/day, which increased to 110 MT/day in 2015 and is expected to reach 126 MT/day by 2019 (ADB, 2012). LMC, today is the third largest waste generated city with 210 tons of daily waste generation (Thapaliya et al., 2024). The rapid increase in plastic consumption has overwhelmed the existing waste management system and to bridge the gap between these challenges, IWWs play a vital role in managing waste.

There are 115 scrap centers and about 8000 IWWs engaged in recovery of recyclables in LMC (Practical Action, 2014). They are among the lowest-paid groups in Nepal, as they make a living out of waste like plastics, irons, and cartoons from highways, rivers, and dumpsites. Additionally, their income varies according to seasons and festivals and heavily depends on the quantity and quality of recyclables (Khanal, 2022; Wilson et al., 2012). These waste workers face substantial socio-economic and health challenges that hinder their ability to operate effectively. IWWs earn low wages, experience limited job security, and lack access to essential health and educational services as they belong to the marginalized community. Due to no formal education and low skills, they are bound to work in such harsh conditions. The hazardous nature of their work exposes them to various health risks, including respiratory diseases, physical injuries, and infections (Maharjan & Lohani, 2019).

Additionally, gender-based disparities are prevalent in the waste management sector, with female waste workers typically engaging in the most labor-intensive and lowest-paying tasks. Although women actively participate in informal waste management systems, their responsibilities are often ignored or replaced by men. They work in lower-level jobs like picking and sorting waste, while men dominate in higher-paying jobs like driving trucks and trading in scrap (UNEP, 2022). Addressing socio-economic challenges, health and safety risks, and gender-based disparities is vital for improving the efficiency of plastic waste recovery. This study aims to address the importance of IWWs and highlight their crucial role in plastic waste management.

1.3 Rationale of the Research

Plastic waste management is a major environmental issue in urban areas of Nepal. While the city struggles to combat the menace of plastic waste, people from vulnerable communities have been showing their impactful role in minimizing and monetizing this environmental issue. Although they are at the forefront of waste management, IWWs are often neglected in the workforce. They bridge the gap that exists between the collecting of waste and its disposal in landfills. In cities like LMC, IWWs play a major role in collecting, sorting, and recycling plastic waste, forming the backbone of the recycling system. However, they continue to face socioeconomic challenges, hazardous working conditions, and no formal recognition.

By focusing on key aspects such as income, working conditions, gender disparities, health and safety, and access to resources, this research will help to identify the challenges faced by IWWs. Handling waste in harsh conditions often exposes waste workers to significant health hazards. But the provisions for adequate safety protocols are yet to be adopted. This shows an alarming need to understand these challenges and assess the level of support available to the workers in terms of health and safety. While considering these factors, it is also important to address operational challenges in the collection and segregation of plastic waste in the scrap centers of LMC. This also helps to reflect the safety measures or facilities currently available to ensure the occupational safety of workers.

The questions or gaps in the study done in previous research related to these topics are addressed in the analysis of data from surveys, interviews, and resources collected. By analyzing the experiences from both IWWs and scrap centers, the research will focus on providing insights on current situation of IWWs and their contribution in plastic waste recovery and circular economy. It highlights how informal efforts in collection, segregation and delivery of recyclable wastes forms an entire recycling chain, from waste collection to its processing in scrap centers and eventually to recycling factories. The research focuses on the interconnections between informal waste workers and their status, challenges, and plastic waste management.

1.4 Objectives of the Research

1.4.1 General Objective of the Research

- To understand the status of informal waste workers in Lalitpur Metropolitan City and their contribution in plastic waste management.

1.4.2 Specific Objective of the Research

- a. To assess the socio-economic status of informal waste workers.
- b. To identify the scenario of occupational health and safety in the plastic waste management sector.
- c. To analyze the influence of gender-based roles and challenges of informal waste workers in plastic waste collection, sorting, and recycling.
- d. To evaluate the contribution of informal waste workers to plastic waste recovery and recycling

1.5 Scope and Limitation of the Research

Lalitpur Metropolitan City is a prominent area within the Kathmandu Valley recognized for its significant population of informal waste workers and evolving waste management practices. Informal Waste Workers are the individuals who collect recyclable and reusable materials outside of the formal economy often with no formal recognition, contract or social benefits. This study specifically focuses IWWs engaged in the collection, segregation, and recycling of plastic waste, encompassing both male and female workers.

The research considers various roles of IWWs within the waste management sector including cycle hawkers, door-to-door waste collectors, primary segregators, secondary segregators, and baling machine operators. In this study, a distinction is made between affiliated waste workers and unaffiliated waste workers. Affiliated waste workers are those who operate under private scrap centers, NGOs, or municipal partnership whereas, unaffiliated waste workers independently collect recyclables from streets or landfills and sell them to scrap dealer with no institutional support. The research explores their current socio-economic conditions, health and safety challenges, and gender inequalities, shedding light on their daily struggles and workplace

hazards. The findings of this study aim to highlight IWWs' contribution in closing the loop of plastic waste by recovering and reintegrating recyclables into production cycle, supporting plastic waste management in LMC.

The following are some of the limitations of the study:

- a. The study was conducted between November and February, with only three weeks dedicated to data collection. This limited timeframe may not have captured all the seasonal or operational variations in the waste management sector.
- b. This study did not cover all wards within the geographical scope of Lalitpur Metropolitan City with a limited sample size; thus, the findings cannot generalize to all informal waste workers, limiting the comprehensiveness of the findings.
- c. Differences in working conditions and practices among various groups, such as bicycle hawkers, primary segregators etc., might draw variation in conclusions or comparisons of the challenges and safety of waste workers. This study might also have not captured all seasonal or operational variation in scrap centers within waste management sector.
- d. The gap in existing research or reliable data of Municipal Solid Waste in LMC made it challenging to understand the scale of waste handled by informal waste workers.
- e. Ongoing issues related to the demolition of scrap centers created a sense of distrust among some scrap centers and informal waste workers, making them hesitant to openly share information.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Literature Review

2.1.1 Introduction of Plastic Waste and Plastic Waste Management

Annually, over 460 tons of plastics are produced globally, with about approximately 20 million metric tons ending up in the environment. The data between 2000 and 2019 shows global plastic production has doubled, reaching 460 million tons (IUCN, 2022). This growing trend of production and consumption of plastics is expected to increase promptly by 2040 (IUCN, 2024). The evolution of plastics began in 1907, initially praised for its affordability; however, the perception shifted with raising environmental concerns. The dependency on plastics, particularly in developing nations, is projected to reach 4 billion per year, doubling municipal solid waste by 2050 (Plastic for Change, 2024).

Countries have gradually adopted initiatives for plastic waste management and enhancing recycling efficiency. European countries such as Sweden and Germany recycle over 50% of waste with stringent regulations and policies in waste management. The European Union produces about 16 million tons of plastic waste, while 6.65 million tons are recycled (European Parliament, 2018). The adoption of Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) laws in France and Germany holds manufacturers responsible for end-of-life product disposal, promoting recyclable designs (Smith et al., 2023). While these countries have made positive strides, the USA and Canada have stagnant recycling rates due to the impact of China's National Sword policy and economic constraints (Canada Plastics Pact, 2024).

According to research from the University of Leeds, uncollected waste primarily causes the greatest vulnerability to plastic pollution. The impact of plastic waste adversely affects emerging countries in the global south. About 1.2 billion people, mainly in developing countries, lack access to adequate waste collection services (The Maritime Executive, 2024). In Brazil, the absence of effective recycling regulations and higher unemployment rates make the waste management sector a major challenge. Likewise, in parts of Africa and South America, informal recycling sectors are not officially recognized, though they have great contributions to waste

management. Rapid industrialization in countries like China and India disrupts waste management initiatives.

The high-income countries have the power to recycle due to their ability to create recycling systems and extend trade agreements with other countries to collect recyclable waste. However, many developing countries like Nepal face obstacles due to inadequate infrastructure or inefficiencies in domestic recycling infrastructure that further worsen regulatory frameworks (TRVST, 2024). As globalization and urbanization continue to expand, the need for effective, efficient, and sustainable plastic waste management systems becomes increasingly critical to address these challenges.

2.1.2 National State of Plastic Waste Management

As urbanization continues to grow, the demand and usages of plastics also intensify, leaving cities in Nepal struggling to manage an estimated 600 metric tons of plastic waste generated daily across landfills (Park et al., 2024). Out of 293 urban local governments, only six have landfill sites, while the rest of them dump waste in open areas. However, these landfill sites have no proper waste disposal methods. Among the dumped waste, around sixteen percent of municipal solid waste comprises plastic, with larger cities producing more waste (ADB, 2013). An urban center like Kathmandu Valley alone generates 0.12 to 0.15 kg of plastic waste per person daily that either ends up in open dumps and rivers or is burned in open air (Poudel et al., 2019).

In Nepal, the Solid Waste Management (SWM) Act and Rules were enacted in 2013 to establish a systematic approach to managing municipal solid waste from households and industries. The SWM Act mandates local bodies to promote the 3Rs—reduce, reuse, and recycle—through waste separation at the source. As the SWM Act was enacted prior to the establishment of a three-tier government system, it failed to acknowledge important waste categories such as electronic, plastic, demolition, and disaster waste. Waste management today is a local challenge that demands coordination and support from both federal and local bodies. To reduce ultra-thin plastic waste, which is difficult to recycle, the government banned the production of bags smaller than 20 microns via the Plastic Bag Regulation and Control Directive in 2011.

Additionally, the import, sale, distribution, and storage of plastic flowers were banned in 2022. Despite plastic accounting for 16% of total waste, these policies are not adequate to mitigate the challenges (ADB, 2013)

Following regulations guides local government bodies in enacting solid waste management procedures in Nepal;

Regulation/Policy	Details
The Constitution of Nepal, 2015	Mandates local governments to manage municipal solid waste, including plastic waste, to ensure public health and environmental protection
List of Power and Unbundling Report (Nepal Ministry of Federal Affairs, and General Administration, 2018)	Policy "Unbundling Report" defines the roles and responsibilities of different levels of government, including waste management duties at local levels
Federal, Provincial, and Local Level Coordination and Interrelation Act, 2077	Facilitates coordination between various government levels to ensure effective solid waste management through clear guidelines on intergovernmental relations
Inter-Governmental Fiscal Transfer Act, 2074	Outlines fiscal transfer mechanisms, ensuring that local governments have the necessary funds to manage waste, including plastics
Solid Waste Management National Policy, 2079 (2022)	Establishes a national strategy for waste management, including goals for waste reduction, recycling, and sustainable disposal methods
Solid Waste Management Act, 2068 (2011)	Provides a legal framework for the proper collection, disposal, and recycling of municipal solid waste, focusing on the responsibility of local governments
Solid Waste Management Rules, 2070 (2013)	Sets detailed operational procedures for waste segregation, collection, disposal, and recycling to enhance waste

	management efficiency at local levels
Local Government Operation Act, 2074 (2018)	Details the roles, functions, and operational procedures of local governments, including their responsibilities in managing solid waste
Environment Protection Act, 2076 (2019)	Provides the framework for environmental protection in Nepal, including specific regulations for waste management and pollution control
Environment Protection Rules, 2077 (2020)	Supports the Environment Protection Act by detailing the steps needed to ensure better waste management practices, reduce pollution, and promote sustainable waste disposal

Table 1 : Solid Waste Management Regulation and policies in Nepal

Regardless of the formulation of several waste management legislations, policies, and directives, Nepal continues to encounter difficulties in its practices. Though the Environment Protection Act 2019 and the Solid Waste Management Act 2011 provide the legal framework for waste management, its effectiveness and implementation still have many loopholes. The capacity and resources of local governments to adequately enforce legislation is weak (The World Bank, 2020). Furthermore, informal recycling industries, which dominate waste management in many regions of Nepal, are not integrated into official systems, leading to shortcomings in waste processing and recycling (ADB, 2013).

2.1.3 Formal and Informal Sector Engagement in Waste Collection in Nepal

Figure 2.1: Material Flow Analysis of Plastics in Nepal (Ghimire & Bajracharya, 2023)

In Nepal, local bodies are primarily responsible for waste collection, from formalized waste collection systems to segregation and waste disposal. Once the wastes are segregated, the non-recyclable are transported to landfills or dumping sites, and recyclable wastes are sold to formal or informal scrap centers or scarp aggregators. The mixed plastics collected in those centers are sorted manually into different types before being sent to the recycling facilities.

The process and mechanism of waste collection differ from municipalities in the core areas of Kathmandu Valley. In some municipalities, a public-private partnership model is operated where the private sector manages tasks such as door-to-door waste collection, street cleaning, and public space maintenance while the municipalities support these efforts by overseeing the transfer of waste from designated collection points to landfill sites (Republica, 2018). IWWs play a crucial role in waste management in Nepal, particularly in collecting and recycling plastics. Among the seven major categories of plastics, PET, HDPE, LDPE, and PP are the most commonly collected, as they are the plastics that are frequently recycled in Nepal.

2.1.4 Challenges Faced by Informal Waste Workers

Waste management involves multiple stakeholders, including government agencies, large private companies, local organizations, and the informal sector. These IWWs play an important role in waste diversion yet are not recognized by the law (Giri et al., 2023; Alam and Ahmade, 2013). Nearly 60% of plastic waste is recovered by waste workers globally, providing economic and environmental benefits (Cambridge University Press, 2023). However, in developing countries like Nepal, a formal regulated system of waste management is absent.

IWWs in Kathmandu Valley handle about 15% of the city's waste, including plastic (Dangi et al., 2015). Beyond collection, they sort recyclable wastes on the ground level, reducing waste going to landfill sites (Neogi, 2000; Pier, 1998). Despite this, the unstructured nature of informal collection leaves waste workers without job security, social benefits, or protection under labor laws (International Labor Organization, 2020). They usually come from low-income families with unstable incomes, high occupational health risks, and inadequate access to their safety. Although aware of these health hazards, most workers—especially those who work in landfills—have no proper safety equipment (Giri et al., 2023; Alam and Ahmade, 2013).

Seasonal variations further affect their income, as the earnings depend on the quantity of recyclables collected (Khanal, 2022; Wilson et al., 2012). Their work exposes them to various health hazards and socioeconomic vulnerabilities. The societal shame connected with waste worsens their difficulties, making it harder to cope with their daily lives (Gutberlet & Uddin, 2018).

2.1.5 Circular Economy and Informal Waste Workers

The central idea of the circular economy challenges the "take-make-consume-dispose" model that assumed resources were abundant and readily available. Circular economy creates a framework for reducing waste, recycling materials, and reusing resources to create a closed-loop economy (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2013). By redefining resource usage and turning waste into recycled raw materials, it addresses concerns about the "decoupling" of resource consumption (UNEP, 2011). This concept lays out the strategies for preventing waste,

prolonging the life of products, recovering resources, and creating a circular system.

Kenneth Boulding introduced the idea of a closed-loop economy in "*The Economics of the Coming Spaceship Earth*" in the nineteenth century, which formed a basis for circular economic principles. Contemporary frameworks, such as those created by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation, emphasize the interaction of environmental and economic systems to preserve material value throughout time (Preston, 2012; Webster, 2015). The goal of the circular economy is to maintain the usability and value of products and resources over time. The circular economy is becoming a key component of international sustainability programs, including the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goal 12 "*Responsible Consumption and Production*" and the European Union's low-carbon economy plan (European Commission, 2015).

To meet the objectives of the circular economy, waste workers are the key players, particularly in low- and middle-income nations, as waste management and recycling activities are run by the informal sector. The gap from plastics disposal in the environment to them reaching the recycling factories is facilitated by waste workers. This effort ensures materials are reintegrated into production cycles rather than being discarded in the environment, supporting the circular loop of resource use.

The transition from perceiving waste as a burden to recognizing it as a resource for useful byproducts coincides with circular economy concepts. This has prompted businesses to incorporate recycling procedures into their operations. In this process, informal waste workers are the key players in creating a closed loop rather than just recovering materials. Circular economy gives equal importance to the safety of the workers, with the need for improved socio-economic conditions and recognition of their contribution to sustainable development.

2.2 Empirical Literature Review

2.2.1 Socio-economic Status of Informal Waste Workers

Traditionally, individuals working in waste sectors were associated with the responsibility of marginalized groups, commonly referred to as "*untouchables*," such as *Chyame* and *Pode*. These groups historically originated from poor socio-economic backgrounds and lived around

the periphery of urban areas with no access to basic facilities and services (Karmacharya, 2022). Research from “*The integration of informal female waste workers in solid waste management of Kathmandu*” revealed that workers earn around NPR 10,000 to 20,000 per month, with their income solely dependent on the quality and quantity of recyclables they collect. Seasonal variation also directly affects their earnings; for instance, 10% is deducted from their wage as wet materials weigh more in the rainy season (Kunwar & Singh, 2021). Additionally, scrap owners exploit waste workers by offering low prices. Due to lower bargaining power, workers are compelled to sell their recyclables at reduced rates. This ultimately perpetuates an unstable cycle of employment, low wages, and exploitation of informal waste workers (Luitel et al., 2011).

The report “*Livelihood and Sustainability of Informal Waste Workers in Kathmandu Valley: A Qualitative Narrative Inquiry*” states that IWWs typically work 5+ hours daily with unstructured and irregular schedules due to the unpredictable nature of the waste collection. Their work is based on the availability of waste, and they struggle to earn NPR 400-600 a day, which hardly meets their daily needs, leaving room for no savings. Since informal waste workers belong to a socioeconomically marginalized group, they are perceived as inferior and have strained relationships with people in their neighborhood (Chaudhary, G., 2023). As a result, “*Risks and risk mitigation in waste work: A qualitative study of informal waste workers in Nepal*” highlights how they often become targets of verbal abuse, being called derogatory names, and physical abuse such as being slapped. Workers, especially from the Madhesh region, are bullied and labeled as migrants from India. Additionally, they are also wrongfully accused of theft and robbery while collecting waste (Sapkota et al., 2020).

Society often perceives their work as “dirty work” and judges them through the lens of stigma and marginalization, deeply rooted in cultural, economic, and social biases. Due to ingrained social, cultural, and economic biases, they are left behind in access to education, employment opportunities, and health care services. The research “*Role of Informal Waste Workers for Sustainable Waste Management in Nigeria and Nepal*” shows how marginalized people must labor in unfavorable conditions to make ends meet. Additionally, the study contrasts how income volatility worsens during festivals and economic downturns intensify income instability

in both countries. They experience payment delays, a lack of adequate benefits, and are unwilling to assert their rights for fear of losing their jobs. This indicates how their socioeconomic weaknesses are taken advantage of with little to no legal assistance and recognition (Khanal et al., 2020).

2.2.2 Occupational Health and Safety Risk of Informal Waste Workers

The waste management practices of two underdeveloped countries, Nigeria and Nepal, are studied in “*Role of Informal Waste Workers for Sustainable Waste Management in Nigeria and Nepal.*” Both countries struggle with inadequate waste management systems, which directly affect collection, and segregation leading to minimal waste reuse. It also explores several risks faced by IWWs who operate within insufficient infrastructure, leading to irregular income, poor living conditions, and significant occupational health risks. Despite being aware of these potential health risks, informal workers barely use safety gear due to high costs and limited availability at scrap centers for their protection, making it impossible for them to regularly replace PPE kits (Khanal et al., 2020).

Many IWWs accept or neglect the hazards, considering them as an unavoidable part of their job. Waste segregation is predominantly performed manually with minimal use of technologies like shredders and balers. This exposes workers to come into direct contact with waste, increasing health and safety concerns (NIDISI, 2023). Most female waste workers were found more conscious than their male counterparts, often wrapping their faces with shawls. However, this is mostly done to avoid being recognized by people. Additionally, the physically demanding nature of the work that requires constant lifting of heavy materials puts a toll on women’s health during the menstrual cycle. IWWs at dumping sites are particularly vulnerable to injuries from vehicles, traffic accidents, and dog bites (Sapkota et al., 2020). According to the study “*Health risks of solid waste management practices in rural Ghana: A semi-quantitative approach toward a solid waste safety plan,*” waste workers are at risk for physical, biological, and chemical harm as the majority of their labor is without protective equipment. This lack of safety protection and measures increases their susceptibility to infections, long-term occupational risks, and other health complications (Vinti et al., 2021).

Exposure to hazardous substances such as lead, mercury, and cadmium in discarded medical and commercial wastes possesses the potential to increase infection rates, including hepatitis B, tuberculosis, and gastrointestinal diseases caused by biological pathogens in waste. However, workers are not informed in this regard. IWWs frequently report chronic joint and back discomfort due to hard lifting and poor posture, as well as a high risk of physical trauma, fractures, and cuts from handling sharp objects (Binion & Gutberlet, 2012). Hospital waste also poses significant health risks due to inadequate waste segregation, lack of occupational safety measures, and weak regulatory enforcement in low-resource settings, leading to infectious and chemical waste (Adewumi et al., 2021).

2.2.3 Gender-Based Roles in Plastic Waste Management

In the waste sector, women primarily hold low-paying responsibilities such as sorting and segregating waste. Their work is often undervalued and less visible, as the majority of male workers are involved in highly demanding roles that involve the collection, sales, and transportation of materials. Thus, male waste workers are paid higher wages compared to female (Kunwar & Singh, 2021; Sapkota et al., 2020). Women juggle between work and household chores, including childcare alongside waste picking. This makes them more vulnerable to wage disparities and exploitation. For safety and social support, women preferred working in groups at centers rather than collecting waste in dumping sites (Binion & Gutberlet, 2012; Sapkota et al., 2020).

Handling dry waste such as plastics and pipes is frequently assigned to women due to sociocultural norms associated with the ownership of heavier or more valuable recyclables to men (Kunwar & Singh, 2021). Men dominate higher-value activities like transporting materials, collecting recyclables in bulk, and bargaining with scrap sellers. These roles are affiliated with higher earnings and relatively greater decision-making power (Sapkota et al., 2020; Vinti et al., 2021). In the waste business, significant earning gaps exist between men and women as women's tasks, such as sorting recyclable plastics into grades, yield lower profit margins than mass recycling or selling plastics to centers, which are largely controlled by male workers (Binion & Gutberlet, 2012).

The study “*Gender and Waste Nexus: Experiences from Bhutan, Mongolia, and Nepal*” reveals how gender, caste, and cultural norms shape the roles and responsibilities of waste workers. In Nepal, marginalized women, particularly those from lower castes, face barriers to jobs with higher salaries due to restrictive caste hierarchies and social class inequalities. Women in this field are burdened with both labor-intensive work and domestic duties, which limits their mobility and opportunities. Due to the stigma attached to waste work, women are disproportionately impacted because their jobs are seen as an extension of household responsibilities rather than as contributions to their profession. The lack of financial literacy makes it more challenging for female workers to access financial resources and credit (GRID-Arendal & UNEP, 2019).

Women in waste have higher burden in segregation, often performed without protective gear while sorting plastic waste. This makes them vulnerable to respiratory diseases, skin infections, and chemical exposure (Binion & Gutberlet, 2012; Vinti et al., 2021). Menstrual hygiene issues make things even more difficult for women who work in informal recycling centers or landfills with poor or nonexistent sanitary facilities (Kunwar & Singh, 2021). Women in waste management suffer societal stigma, restricted educational possibilities, and financial support, perpetuating a cycle of exclusion (Binion & Gutberlet, 2012).

2.2.4 Contribution of Waste Workers in Plastic Waste Management

The unregulated system and operations of local scrap centers result in significant financial interruptions. However, the contribution of IWWs to plastic waste management is undeniable. Approximately 6.43% of waste is recovered and utilized, leaving 22.56% of waste uncollected and unrecycled. *Kabadi shops* operate without formal integration into established waste management systems, further accelerating these inefficiencies (Islam et al., 2008).

According to the study “*Status and Potential of Resource Recovery from Municipal Solid Waste in Kathmandu Valley, Nepal*,” there are between 700–800 scrap centers employing 10,000 and 15,000 IWWs in the valley. On average, 140 metric tons of materials are collected daily, generating livelihoods for these IWWs. The total revenue generated from all the recovered materials from MSW in Kathmandu Valley is estimated at NPR 55.6 million per month, which

includes plastics, paper, metals, and glass. This generates NPR 15.3 million in profit per month and contributes to NPR 4.36 million as tax revenue monthly. This amount could be further increased if the potential for waste recovery is fully recognized (Pathak, 2019).

Similarly, the study "*Life Cycle Assessment of Municipal Plastic Waste Management in Kathmandu.*" states that informal waste pickers recover about 1 metric ton of recyclables daily from Kathmandu Metropolitan City's (KMC), largely unstructured waste management system (Khanal & Ojha, 2023). According to the "*Study of Scrap Waste in Kathmandu Valley,*" cycle hawkers collect 41% of scrap waste directly from households. These hawkers supply materials to scrap centers that employ five to ten people and provide a livelihood for marginalized groups. Locally, glass bottles are recycled; however, recyclables like plastics are exported to be processed into pellets. Despite their contributions, the lack of formal integration limits the efficiency and scale of their operations (Luitel & Khanal, 2010).

Inadequate waste segregation at source remains a challenge for material recovery and recycling activities, which is highlighted in the study conducted in Lalitpur Metropolitan City Ward 14. Landfilling is still the major component of the present MSW management practices that contribute to resource recovery problems and environmental deterioration. From the study "*Municipal Solid Waste Management in Nepal: Opportunities and Challenges,*" it can be noted that most municipalities in Nepal depend on a primitive system of waste collection and landfill disposal without segregation or treatment, which ultimately leads to landfill disposal with minimum emphasis on segregation or treatment (Maharjan et al., 2023). Even though local authorities in Nepal are responsible for handling solid wastes, including collection, classification, and disposal, implementation of this seems lacking. Non-recyclable wastes are disposed of in landfills, while recyclables are segregated at source and sold to scrap centers or aggregators. There is a need for integrated waste management approaches, including proper segregation and infrastructure investments such as material recovery facilities for sorting recyclables and sanitary landfills for non-recyclables (Maharjan & Lohani, 2019).

The research paper "*Waste Pickers of Nepal*" classifies informal waste workers into affiliated and unaffiliated waste pickers. Affiliated workers are those who work for private firms or other formal collection systems. However, their working circumstances are frequently informal and

lack social and economic protection, even when they are affiliated with private entities. Workers who are self-employed and not affiliated with any formal organization or system, such as those who collect recyclables from streets or landfills and sell them to scrap dealers, are considered unaffiliated. Any institutions do not support their work; instead, they rely on sales to make money (Bajracharya, Koirala, & Rayamajhi, 2022).

A gap in the literature review is observed as waste workers are broadly categorized into single groups despite having divergent roles in waste collection and management. Different IWWs, such as door-to-door collectors, waste segregators, cycle hawkers etc., collect and manage waste with varying tasks and responsibilities that are closely tied to financial returns and health risks. For example, cycle hawkers collect residential wastes, waste workers in the center deal with dry waste segregation, balers handle large volumes of recyclable materials, etc.

Furthermore, little research has been done on whether IWWs have been benefited by institutional support or training programs to improve their socioeconomic status and working conditions. While some studies shed light on women's roles in waste management and associated health hazards in the workplace, menstrual hygiene issues caused by a lack of sufficient sanitation facilities at work sites have received little attention. Additionally, there is little emphasis on whether IWWs are informed about, or have access to, insurance programs that could offer financial protection in the event of an accident or health difficulties.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

A non-experimental, descriptive research design was formulated for the research. This study uses a mixed-method approach, combining qualitative and quantitative techniques to analyze research questions. Data were gathered from primary and secondary sources, and the statistical interpretation method was used to interpret and analyze the data. The quantitative indicator includes employment status, income levels, including average earnings, gender distribution, health coverage such as insurance access and checkup facilities, and operational details like the amount of plastic waste recovered and recycled daily. The qualitative indicators focus on gender roles and responsibilities of waste workers, along with occupational challenges such as workplace hazards, stigma, and health risks. The overall working conditions were also observed to analyze and understand the ground realities of waste workers.

3.2 Study Area, Population and Sample Size

a. Study Area:

Figure 3.1: Map of Study Area

Lalitpur Metropolitan City is in the south-central region of the Kathmandu Valley. It is divided into 29 wards. This study was conducted across 6 wards of LMC, focusing on IWWs engaged in the collection, segregation, and recycling of plastic waste

- b. **Population:** There are 97 scrap centers in Lalitpur Metropolitan City with a total of 1700 informal waste workers (University of Leeds, 2024). The targeted population for this study includes IWWs specifically involved in collecting and managing plastic waste within LMC.
- c. **Sample Size:** Using statistical calculation, a sample size of 66 waste workers was selected for the survey.

The formula used for determining the sample size is:

$$n = \frac{z^2 \times \hat{p}(1 - \hat{p})}{\epsilon^2}$$

where,

n = required sample size

z = z-score for the desired confidence level (1.645 for 90% confidence)

p = estimated population proportion (1700 informal waste workers)

ε = margin of error (10%)- paper

3.3 Sampling Method

3.3.1 Convenient Sampling

Convenient sampling was used to select participants based on accessibility and relevance to the study. IWWs from various backgrounds and roles within LMC engaged in collecting and managing plastic wastes were chosen. The information on scrap centers from LMC was collected, and phone calls were made to identify centers in plastic waste management as per convenience. Then, the survey of IWWs from these centers was undertaken.

3.4 Data Collection Source

The research has taken into account primary and secondary sources for data in the following ways:

- a. **Primary Source:** Primary data were collected through a structured questionnaire survey, interview of Scrap Center Owner and Key Informant Interview (KII) and the Environmental Chief Officer of LMC.
- b. **Secondary Source:** Secondary data were collected from online sources such as academic journals, research reports, policy briefs, previous thesis studies, and newspaper articles.

3.5 Data Collection Methods

3.5.1 Primary Data Collection Method

Tools Used	Respondents	No. of Respondents	Means of Collection
Questionnaire Survey	Informal waste workers from Ward no. 2, Ward no. 3, Ward no. 8, Ward no. 9, Ward no. 17, Ward no. 23	66	Physical
Interview and Key Informant Interview (KII)	Interview: Scarp Center Owners from Ward no. 2, Ward no. 3, Ward no. 8, Ward no. 9, Ward no. 17, Ward no. 23	6	Physical
	KII: Environmental Chief Officer of Lalitpur Metropolitan City	1	Physical

Table 2: Primary source of data collection

3.5.2 Secondary Data Collection Method:

Secondary data collection tools used in the study is mostly published academic journals, research reports, published articles, policy briefs, and newspaper articles.

3.6 Ethical Considerations

Before any data collection, all respondents were provided with informed verbal consent. The objective of the study was explained to informal waste workers and scrap center owners, and only their voluntary participation was agreed to, with the choice to leave the discussion at any time. The study strictly maintains confidentiality and anonymity, ensuring that identities and sensitive information are protected, especially considering the marginalized status of many informal waste workers. Also, photographs and audio recordings of KII were taken after the approval from each of the respondents.

3.7 Data Management and Analysis:

3.7.1 Processing Operations

a. **Arrangement of Data:**

The large set of data collected from IWWs was noted down during the survey and then later transcribed and maintained in a structured text form format, and the data were then entered in the Excel spreadsheet and were cleaned. The audio recordings from KII were transcribed according to questionnaire responses along with the additional notes

b. **Coding:**

The quantitative data were coded and put into a limited number of categories by assigning numerical values. Coding was necessary for efficient analysis as the responses covered a wide range of inputs. Coding it into a small number of classes maintained the critical information required for analysis.

c. **Classification:**

After the data were coded, it was arranged into different groups and categories as per the requirement of the objective. This involved identifying and classifying the data based on characteristics and assigning suitable alpha-numeric characters to the collected data.

a. **Tabulation:**

Quantitative data were analyzed using Excel, which are presented in the tabular and graphical representations. Qualitative data have been processed to provide a descriptive analysis for the given topics.

Chapter 4: Result and Discussion

4.1 Socio-economic Aspect of the Informal Waste Workers

4.1.1 Socio-Demographic Profile of Informal Waste Workers

A total of 66 waste workers aged 18 to 58 were surveyed during the study, out of which 47 were male IWWs and 19 were female IWWs. A detailed description of demographic and social characteristics is given in *Table No. 3* below.

Variables	Group	Male		Female		Total	
		Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Affiliation	Unaffiliated	13	28%	8	42%	21	32%
	Affiliated	34	72%	11	58%	45	68%
Age Group	18-28	6	13%	5	26.3%	11	17%
	28-38	24	51%	8	42.2%	32	48%
	38-48	15	32%	5	26.3%	20	30%
	48-58	2	4%	1	5.2%	3	5%
Nationality	Nepali	26	55%	18	95%	44	67%
	Indian	21	45%	1	5%	22	33%
Marital Status	Single	5	11%	3	16%	8	12%
	Married	42	89%	14	74%	56	85%
	Divorced/Separated	0	0%	1	5%	1	1.5%
	Widowed	0	0%	1	5%	1	1.5%
	No formal education	22	47%	14	74%	36	55%
Education	Primary education	23	49%	5	26%	28	42%
	Secondary education	2	4%	0	0%	2	3%

Types of Waste Workers	Mixed Waste Segregators	0	0%	8	42%	8	12%
	Recyclable Segregators	12	25%	11	58%	23	35%
	Cycle Hawkers	13	28%	0	0%	13	20%
	Door-to-door collector	9	19%	0	0%	9	13%
	Baling Machines Operators	13	28%	0	0%	13	20%

Table 3: Demographics of the Respondents

4.1.2 Affiliation of Waste Workers

From this data, two types of workers were identified: affiliated waste workers and unaffiliated waste workers. 68% were affiliated workers, who worked in scrap centers with no formal contract and lacked a social safety net. While 32% of respondents were unaffiliated waste workers, who earned daily wages on the basis of the amount of waste they collected. All of the respondents were hired only on the basis of verbal agreement.

Affiliated waste workers operated in scrap centers, including recyclable segregators (secondary segregators), door-to-door collectors, baling machine operators, and segregators. The findings revealed that even though they worked in local centers, their employment condition remain largely informal with no proper basic facilities, making them vulnerable to exploitation.

In contrast, unaffiliated waste workers worked independently on a daily basis, as cycle hawkers and mixed waste segregators (primary aggregators) providing uncertainty and temporary opportunities to earn a living. These workers face greater challenges in terms of vulnerability and exploitation than affiliated waste workers, as their income is directly related to the fluctuating availability of resources.

4.1.3 Age Group

Figure 4.1 : Age Distribution of informal waste workers from the survey

The majority of IWWs comprise the age group of 28-38, with 48% of total workers. This is followed by the age group of 38-48 with 30% of the total respondents. The younger group of 18-28 represents a total of 17% while a smaller portion of 5% are from 48-58 years. There are no workers above the age of 58. This data shows that waste management is dominated by people aged 28-38, as it is considered the prime working years to provide for the family. There is a significant decline in the representation of people in the age group of 48-58 and no waste workers above the age of 58. This indicates the physically intensive nature of this work that discourages people from the older age group to continue working in laborious jobs.

4.1.4 Nationality

The data suggests a higher reliance on Nepali workers, with 66% of total respondents in waste collection and management practices. However, 33% of the Indian workforce showcases the cross-border labor movement in search of economic opportunities. Unfortunately, Indian workers face discrimination and negative stereotyping not just in the workplace but also by the people in the community. During the survey, they mentioned about the unfair treatment due to their nationality by mocking them while collecting waste. One respondent also shared their experience when someone threw water at them while collecting the waste. Such behavior shows the discouragement the Indian workers face, affecting their morale. This aligns with the findings

of Sapkota et al. (2020) that Indian workers face societal discrimination and are mistreated and subjected to verbal abuse, called derogatory names, and accused of theft and robbery.

4.1.5 Affiliation of the Ethnicity of Respondents

Figure 4.2 : Ethnicity of Informal Waste Workers from the survey

The data on the ethnic composition of IWWs shows that the majority of the population is from the Janajati community, with 45%. A notable population of Indian respondents are mostly from Bihar, with 33%. IWWs migrate to Nepal for waste-related work due to financial necessity, as job opportunities are easier due to rising labor demand. They also shared that they prefer working distant from home to avoid stigma and judgements associated with waste work by their community. Only a small proportion of 2% of the population belongs to Brahmins and Muslim backgrounds. The Janajati community, largely due to socioeconomic factors and limited access to alternative opportunities, is engaged in labor-intensive jobs like waste collection and management. Also, marginalized groups have access to fewer resources and societal challenges, making them inclined to work in waste. Khanal et al. (2020) also explain the intersectionality of caste to economic vulnerability that creates barriers, leaving them in waste management as only a few viable options.

4.1.6 Marital Status

Figure 4.3: Marital status of Informal Waste Workers from the survey

The data shows the majority of IWWs are married, accounting for 56 out of 66 respondents from the survey. This includes 42 married men and 14 married women. 8% of the respondents are single, including 5 males and 3 females. One female respondent each, separated and widowed, were reported, constituting 1.5% each. The married population is the highest for both genders, showing a strong representation of the responsibility of family that comes along with it. The 1.5% of both divorced and widowed waste workers were the sole breadwinners of the family. IWWs face direct societal judgements, greater household responsibilities and financial challenges to support their family, potentially further pushing them into the waste sector.

4.1.7 Educational Status

Figure 4.4: Education Level of the Informal Waste Workers

The data highlights the education level among the waste workers is low, with 22 male and 14 female respondents with no formal education. The highest level of education of waste workers is primary education, with a total of 23 males and 5 females. While only 2 male workers have attained secondary education. Also, none of the respondents have pursued a higher level of education. This finding shows that males have slightly higher education than females, particularly in primary education and secondary education.

The educational gap among the IWWs attributes to poverty, causing early entry into the labor market. The survey revealed that many workers in the waste sector lack basic literacy, leading to low-paying jobs. Kunwar & Singh (2021) stated that the waste sector is predominated by people from marginalized backgrounds and deprived of educational opportunities. With no formal educational background, this job is the last option for the workers. Women have lower educational attainment than male which influenced by socio-cultural norms and societal biases, as highlighted by Khanal et al. (2020).

4.1.8 Living Arrangements of Informal Waste Workers

Figure 4.5.: Living Arrangement of Informal Waste Workers

68% of respondents lived in rented rooms who migrated from remote areas seeking job opportunities in waste management. They worked to pay rent, cover daily expenses, and sustain families. 20% of total IWWs lived in scrap centers with a significant portion being cycle hawkers with no proper basis facilities. While 12% of IWWs lived in scrap centers with fooding and accommodations provided by the center. All of the workers who lived in the scrap centers were Indian waste workers. While none of the workers owned homes or resided in temporary shelters.

Unaffiliated workers i.e., cycle hawkers, lived in scrap centers with no support from employers which provided greater burden and unstable incomes. While affiliated waste workers received support from employers in both accommodation and food. However, this arrangement may lead to dependency on employers, increasing vulnerability to job security and exploitation These workers may lose access to both basic facilities and livelihood if their jobs are terminated. On the other hand, most IWWs complained about constant financial stress due to high living costs in Kathmandu Valley.

4.2 Primary Roles in Plastic Waste Management

Role of waste workers	Male	Female	Total
Mixed Waste Segregators (Primary Segregators)	0	8	8
Recyclables Segregators (Secondary Segregators)	12	11	23
Cycle Hawkers	13	0	13
Door-to-door collector	9	0	9
Baling Machines Operators	13	0	13
Total	47	19	66

Table 4: Primary Roles of Informal Waste Workers in Plastic Waste Management

The mixed waste workers (primary segregators) represent 8 female respondents, recyclable segregators (secondary segregators) consist of 23 respondents, and door-to-door collectors had a total of 9 respondents. Similarly, baling machine operators constitute a total of 13 male respondents. From the survey, all these IWWs had distinct responsibilities and working conditions.

- a. **Mixed Waste Segregators:** Commonly known as primary segregators, they collect and segregate the recyclable wastes from the pile of both organic and inorganic wastes, which requires labor-intensive work often undertaken by women. This is also discussed in the findings of the CREASION (2022) report, which explains the significant health risks caused by direct contact with hazardous waste.
- b. **Cycle Hawkers and Door-to-Door Collectors:** The mobility of these workers allows them to travel to broader networks for the collection of waste sources, but the difference is that Cycle Hawkers collect dry recyclable wastes, while Door-to-Door

Collectors collect mixed household wastes. This work is primarily dominated by males, as this requires greater physical labor and mobility, which is often restricted for women by societal pressure. From the study of Kunwar & Singh (2021), these workers are widely exposed to risks like traffic accidents and harassment.

- c. Secondary Segregators:** Secondary segregators can also be known as recyclable segregators, primarily sorting recyclables into distinct categories, commonly PET (water bottles) and HDPE (detergent bottles). This helps in the efficiency of recycling processes, which also require dual laborious work such as loading and unloading of waste materials.
- d. Baling Machine Operators:** Baling machine operators specialize in compacting mostly PET bottles baled into baling machines. This requires operating in machines that provide stable yet physically demanding roles compared to others. Thus, this remains less accessible to women as these roles are tied to cultural norms and limited technical knowledge.

Figure 4.6: Distinct tasks of informal waste workers from collection to recycling

This figure 4.6, illustrates the entire cycle of different IWWs, from the collection of discarded waste to its segregation and the process of sending it for recycling, highlighting their distinct task divisions in the waste management system. The data showed that most males are involved in the collection and segregation of waste, such as door-to-door collectors and cycle hawkers. On the other hand, the majority of the women were engaged in sorting and segregation of mixed waste as primary segregators. Meanwhile, majority of male performed segregation and loading/unloading of recyclables as secondary segregators, and baling machine operators baled the recyclable plastics into a compact form for sending it to the recycling facilities. This shows male dominance in tasks such as collection, segregation, loading, and unloading, as they required greater physical intensity. Likewise, most women respondents were involved in segregation only.

4.3 Employment Status of Informal Waste Workers

4.3.1 Work Experience and Working Hours of Informal Waste Workers

Figure 4.7: Work Experience of Informal Waste Workers in Waste Management (In years)

Based on the data, there is a distinct dominance of male workers in the waste management sector; in the category of 6–9 years of experience, there are 18 male respondents, while no

females are present in this group. 21 respondents have worked for more than 9 years, with 17 male and 4 female workers showing disproportionate representation of genders for long tenures. In the 4–6 year category, there is a balanced proportion with 8 males and 7 females. With a higher percentage of women in the less than a year and 1-3 year categories, it can be observed that there is easy entry and exit access among the female waste workers with shorter tenures of involvement.

Figure 4.8: Working hours of Informal Waste Workers per day

A significant number of respondents reported working more than 8 hours daily, making up 58% of the respondents. This shows the need for long and intensive work among the IWWs, regardless of gender. On the other hand, only 8 workers, covering 12% of respondents, work 4–8 hours daily. This pattern among the responses shows that females tend to work shorter hours due to the dual role of household chores and work responsibilities. Since the work demands both time and physical labor, it makes it difficult for women to sustain themselves in this field in the long run. Long working hours to receive minimum earnings and fulfilling household duties create a physical burden and mental and emotional stress. The dominance of women in the early stages reflects the socio-economic necessities. However, the higher percentage of males shows their greater physical strength and the expectation of society to continuously support their families.

4.3.2 Monthly Income from Waste Management

Monthly Income	Total	Male	Female
NPR 10,001-20,000	25	7	18
NPR 20,001-30,000	41	40	1

Table 5: Salary of Respondent

The data shows that 25 respondents received between NPR 10,001 and 20,000, which is barely sufficient for IWWs to cover needs like rent, food, education, and health facilities. Similarly, 41 workers make between NPR 20,001 and 30,000, which offers a marginally better financial situation but is still not sufficient to cover all essential needs.

Since the majority of employees are married, they are responsible for their children and their families. The lack of high-paying prospects in this sector restricts their ability to advance economically and ensure their long-term financial stability. Waste workers operate informally with no social benefits or employment security. Seasonal variations, waste availability, and market demand for waste materials are the main causes of the ongoing income volatility. There is a lack of structured employment benefits or increment possibilities, causing their economic status to repeat in a cycle. Most workers do not earn a sufficient amount, they only make enough to survive. This low economic dependence on daily incomes to survive in Kathmandu Valley limits their ability to break out of poverty cycles.

Additionally, 56 stated that there are pay differences between genders, while the remaining ten stated that there is no pay-wage disparity. Only workers in the unaffiliated sector responded that they earn based on the amount collected. However, it was clear that the majority of IWWs in the affiliated sector, particularly women, are paid less than men. In most scrap centers, women were paid between NPR 400-600, while males were paid between NPR 800-1000 per day. Men performed heavier tasks and received higher compensation, while women's work was considered "lighter," resulting in lower wages. Socio-cultural norms also constrict the mobility of women in roles that require traveling and handling machines, limiting their opportunities for higher wages.

4.3.3 Regularity of Income of Informal Waste Workers

Figure 4.9: Income payment system of Informal waste workers

Out of 66 IWWs, 43 respondents received a monthly salary, while 23 respondents were paid on a daily basis. According to the survey, unaffiliated workers such as cycle hawkers and primary segregators depend on a daily wage system. Their earnings are linked with the quantity and quality of plastic waste they collect. Collected plastics are priced from 2.5-15 NRP per kilogram for PET and HDPE, respectively depending upon the scrap center and roles of IWWs. Due to market-driven prices and seasonal variation, there is financial instability, especially among daily wage workers such as primary segregators and cycle hawkers, providing them low bargaining power. This aligns with the study of Luitel et al. (2011) from the literature review. This fluctuation in price directly affects their wages because their earnings depend solely on the availability of waste. Affiliated workers highlighted that although they have a monthly payment system, they mostly face delays, which make it difficult to preplan their expenditure. The results of this survey support Chaudhary's (2023) conclusions that workers have either a structured income (monthly) or performance-based earnings (daily salary) and absence of weekly or irregular payment.

4.3.4 Work Status of Informal Waste Workers

None of the workers are employed in a contract-based system but are hired on the basis of verbal agreement. As a result, they work in an informal setting with greater flexibility but lack formal employment opportunities. Most respondents complained about irregular income, no social support, and lack of legal recognition. There are no formal hiring practices in centers; no official records are maintained, i.e., no written agreements. This leads to several complications, the first being the irregularity in income. Though the job may offer workers greater control over working hours or flexibility, it comes at the cost of job insecurity and exposure to occupational hazards with no formal support. This limits their opportunity for upward mobility, making their occupation undervalued and unsupported.

4.4 Access to Banking Services

Figure 4.10: Access to Banking Services

Only 14% of the respondents had access to banking services, while 86% respondents had no formal banking access. During the survey, only one female had a bank account to collect widow allowance.

Male workers struggle to save due to rising rental, food, and educational expenses, with only NPR 1000-3,000 available, fluctuating based on needs. The majority of women participate in unofficial saving groups, saving between NPR 500 and NPR 1000 monthly. However, these

groups are not integrated into the current financial system, highlighting a significant disparity in access to financial services and financial literacy. Similarly, few male waste workers were observed engaging in alcohol consumption, claiming they had no savings as they spent most of their money on alcohol.

IWWs often struggle to access formal loans due to a lack of collateral, as their expenses often outweigh their savings. As a result, they rely on borrowing from friends and family for basic living expenses. This economic vulnerability among the IWWs might impact them in unpredictable future circumstances.

4.5 Job Security

Job Assurance	Affiliated		Unaffiliated		Total	%
	Male	Female	Male	Female		
Very Secure	0	0	0	0	0	0
Secure	1	0	0	0	1	1.5%
Somewhat Secure	20	4	2	3	29	44%
Insecure	13	7	11	5	36	55%
Looking for another option	0	0	0	0	0	0%

Table 6: Responses of Informal Waste Workers for Job Security

The findings revealed that 55% of IWWs feel insecure in their jobs. This shows that more than half the total respondents are not satisfied with the work they do. A notable number of respondents, 44%, feel “somewhat secure” with their work. While only 2% of the total respondents feel “secure” working in the waste management sector. Even though these responses indicate that workers are “somewhat secure” or “secure,” they believe their work is stable compared to having no jobs at all. The following table shows the responses of workers pertaining to their job security.

Statements like "*With no formal education and nothing, at least we are working here*" reveal that, though informal, it provides them a livelihood. This is rooted from the perspective of workers, where their job security is not measured by facilities and support but by the opportunities to earn a daily income despite uncertainties. The recyclable wastes, such as plastics and metals, from households were segregated at source by door-to-door collectors, then sold to local scrap centers. One respondent shared that the organic wastes are used as feed in their pig farm. This provided additional income to the workers diversifying their sources. However, this confirms that working in waste management alone does not provide job satisfaction and security.

4.6 Occupational Health and Safety Risks

4.6.1 Common Workplace Hazards Faced by Waste Workers

Thematic Area	Common Hazards	Number of Respondents	Responses
Physical Injuries	Cuts and wounds from sharp objects (glass, syringes, metal scraps)	66	<i>"We get cuts and minor injuries almost every week. Even when we are severely injured, we only get TT injections. There is no proper first aid or support."</i>
Chemical Exposure	Exposure to toxic chemicals (pesticides, disinfectants, industrial waste)	40	<i>"Once, while sorting waste, I unknowingly handled an expired disinfectant bottle that was not empty. The liquid spilled on my hands, causing burning and itching for days."</i>
Infectious Diseases	Infections or diseases from handling contaminated waste	37	<i>"We work with our bare hands. I often get skin infections, and there is no place to wash our hands properly after work."</i>
Extreme Weather Conditions	Heat stress, dehydration, cold-related illnesses, and respiratory issues due to extreme weather	40	<i>"We work in an open space without shade. In summer, we feel dizzy and dehydrated, and in winter, our hands freeze while sorting waste."</i>
Chronic Body Pain & Respiratory Issues	Chronic body pain from heavy lifting, exposure to dust and fumes	54	<i>"The long hours of bending and lifting make my back and knees hurt constantly. Sometimes, I can't even sleep properly because of the pain."</i>

Table 7: Common Hazards faced by the workers in the workplace

The findings from all the respondents confirmed that they faced multiple occupational hazards and unsafe working conditions due to exposure to hazardous waste and the absence of health care support. Physical injuries are a routine part of waste workers, frequently exposing them to deep cuts and bruises. However, they continue to work without proper treatment, relying on TT injections as the only source of medical sources. Binion & Gutberlet (2012) also emphasized the risk of improper disposal of medical waste and poor waste segregation as major causes of injury among IWWs. Sapkota et al. (2020) stated that these injuries increase the possibility of hepatitis B, tuberculosis, and bacterial infections. From the survey, only a few respondents were cautious of Tetanus while still unaware of other risks.

Most workers were observed operating in open spaces with light clothes. This makes them highly susceptible to cuts, dehydration, heat exhaustion in the summer, and joint pain in the winter. The rain makes the handling of waste more challenging as the wet waste is heavier and emits a stronger odor, causing nausea and vomiting. Such exposure to extreme weather conditions over a long period is confirmed to cause chronic health problems like cardiovascular stress and respiratory diseases. Waste workers manually collect and carry heavy loads of plastic; this causes sore aches, muscle strain, and joint pain. The high level of exposure to fine dust particles while sorting waste causes chronic coughing and lung irritation. Based on the findings, all workers accept injuries as an unavoidable part of their job due to a lack of availability of gloves, boots, and masks. According to interview, employees do not consider themselves responsible for providing basic PPE because they are paid for their work. As a result, avoiding occupational dangers is nearly impossible. This illustrates how the worker's health and safety are compromised and how their marginalized status is exploited.

4.6.2 Access to Health and Safety

None of the workers reported having access to health services, which indicates that IWWs do not receive any medical check-ups, vaccinations, or employer-provided healthcare facilities despite their operation in hazardous environments. The absence of provision for health services increases the risk of untreated injuries that could lead to long-term occupational hazards. During the survey, no first aid kit or supplies were observed for primary treatment at the workplace. This suggests that laborers rely on self-medication or avoid seeking medical treatments. As a

result, untreated, minor injuries may lead to severe health complications. The findings suggest that most IWWs do not prioritize their health, stating that their bodies have adapted to working in such unhygienic settings. This aligns with the study that highlights IWWs work without any safety equipment such as gloves, boots, masks, or protective gear (Khanal et al., 2020; Sapkota et al., 2020). This shows that workers themselves are ignorant of their health.

4.6.3 Access to Safety Equipment

Figure 4.11: Access to Safety Equipment

The data shows only 14%, i.e., 9 out of 66 respondents, have access to safety equipment, while the rest received no protective gear from their employers. Door-to-door collectors were provided with only gloves as protective gear. This indicates a serious lack of understanding about the necessity of worker safety equipment. According to scrap center owners, these gloves, boots, and masks wear out quickly and are impossible to provide regularly. Because of this, most workers either ignore using them or purchase them themselves. Few workers who self-purchased protective gear complained that they could not afford regular replacements. Thus, most workers were handling hazardous waste with bare hands and unprotected feet. This increases the frequency of cuts and wounds from sharp objects and direct exposure to biological and chemically contaminated waste.

The survey revealed that 15% of workers received safety equipment from non-governmental organizations. Although these organizations contributed to worker safety, they stated that their

help was inconsistent and inadequate to meet the needs of all workers. The physically intensive nature of the task makes it unattainable to use the provided gloves, masks, and boots for a long period. These supplies from organizations are infrequent and often one-time distribution. After the donated gear is damaged, these workers are left with no protection for an extended period of time. The reliance on "other" means that workers reuse old or discarded boots and gloves from the waste, which is unhygienic and unsafe. The unavailability of safety equipment forces IWWs to use improvised or worn-out materials, offering minimal protection and increasing occupational risks.

Despite being aware of the risks associated with working without gear, IWWs continue to work owing to economic pressures. Employees take advantage of these vulnerabilities, which cause occupational hazards. Interview with scrap center owners, asserted that workers must protect themselves from danger because they provide payment. This indicates a clear disregard for worker safety, putting them in uncertainty.

4.6.4 Training on Safety Protocols Among Waste Workers

Figure 4.12: Training on Safety Protocols among Waste Workers

The findings show that 27% of the respondents received training on safety protocols; most workers have never received any form of safety training. Workers who received training did not receive it from their employers but from external organizations. Basic safety precautions, health hazards, and emergency assistance treatments were covered in the training sessions. Health

check-ups and awareness programs on disease prevention were also conducted. However, these NGOs' seminars are one-time events and do not reach all workers, leaving many without essential knowledge on how to manage hazardous material responsibly.

According to the LMC Environmental Chief Officer, lunch programs were planned with monetary incentives to encourage waste workers to participate. Training included health check-up facilities and interactions with the workers. Nevertheless, these programs are conducted once in a while, which hinders their ability to effectively address the ongoing health and safety issues they face. Workers are compelled to rely on their experiences, as no training is provided for safely handling hazardous wastes. They are unaware of the benefits of wearing protective gear, such as boots, masks, and gloves, as none of the workers are instructed about their significance. This highlights a gap in occupational health and safety education among informal waste workers.

4.6.5 Injury Support for Informal Waste Workers

Figure 4.13: Injury Support for Informal Waste Workers

According to the data, the majority of employees, 97%, relied entirely on their personal finances to cover their work-related conditions. This indicates a severe lack of financial and medical support from employers or external support. The fact that none of the workers mentioned having

relatives or friends to help them highlights how vulnerable they are financially. Only two IWWs, 3%, reported receiving support during the COVID-19 pandemic. This implies that rather than continuous support, employer-provided assistance is rare and situational. Without financial support for injury management, IWWs face significant challenges but continue to work despite their health issues to save their jobs.

4.6.6 Awareness of Health or Accidental Insurance Policies

Figure 4.14: Awareness of Health and Accidental Insurance Policies

The results indicate that there is a significant lack of knowledge and accessibility about health or accident insurance coverage. Only 16 out of 66 waste workers are aware of the health or accidental insurance policy. This implies that there is a major gap in understanding and guidance regarding insurance coverage among waste workers. Without knowledge, no worker can obtain insurance, and without insurance, any medical emergency or workplace injuries cannot be claimed, leaving the worker unprotected. According to interview, a few social entrepreneurs or organizations have provided training or limited insurance coverage for their workers, i.e., affiliated waste workers. However, there is no formal insurance system for a large number of unaffiliated waste workers. The inability of NGOs, government, and insurance companies to coordinate with waste workers further restricts access to safety nets.

4.6.7 Access Health or Accidental Insurance Policies

Figure 4.15: Accessibility to Insurance Facilities

Only 7 out of 66 respondents, 11% of total respondents, have access to accidental insurance, which was provided by an NGO. This shows that 89% of the workers are financially unprotected in case of any workplace injuries. Some organizations play a limited but crucial role for the security of waste workers, although their reach remains small. However, their support is not sustainable but is often part of small-scale projects or one-time initiatives. Further, none of the workers had self-financed insurance due to economic hardships as they struggled to meet daily expenses.

Workers without health or accidental insurance bear the full medical cost, preventing them from seeking medical treatments. One waste worker responded, *“Months ago, I had a cut on my left finger; however, over time the pain worsened and my entire hand stopped moving. I continued to work with my right hand. I was later diagnosed with a severe infection permanently damaging my finger.”* This confirms that a lack of insurance forces workers to choose short-term income over long-term well-being. All workers shared that they continue to work despite injuries and take medical assistance only in absolute scenarios. No financial security of IWWs results in a vulnerability cycle; they work regardless of hazardous circumstances with no possibility of medical access.

Since IWWs have no formal records with municipalities or scrap centers, they lack labor support and protection. The LMC Environmental Chief Officer mentioned that these workers were provided an insurance scheme under the PRISM project. This premium scheme was introduced to encourage savings in cooperative accounts. IWWs were provided with ID cards for healthcare services and medical support to ensure affordable healthcare. However, this initiative was implemented from 2011 to 2014, which merely supported the existing IWWs. This shows how most of the projects are one-time initiatives and are not sustainable in the long-run.

4.6.8 Types of Support Needed for Risk Reduction

Figure 4.16: Needs of Informal Waste Workers for Risk Reduction

The results from the survey showed the needs of waste workers needed to lessen their occupational hazards. 57 IWWs responded, saying that the immediate need regarding safety equipment must be provided with masks, gloves, and boots. Given the risks to their work, the protective gear will not just minimize their rate of injury but also develop more efficiency with a safety consideration. This is followed by the need for accessible health services—free or reasonably affordable health services—with 52 responses. The above findings confirm the gap in the needs and affordability of the healthcare system among the workers. This concerns the need for subsidized healthcare services with immediate health and safety support through the

government. Only 24 responses focused on training on proper handling of waste. This either indicates that workers already have knowledge and experience, or they assume that their current techniques are sufficient. The low priority for training might also indicate that IWWs choose tangible support, such as safety equipment, over skill development programs.

4.7 Gender Disparities in Work among Male and Female Workers

4.7.1 Gender Division of Labor

Figure 4.17: Gender division of labor between male and female waste workers

86% of IWWs believed that gender had a direct impact on jobs and responsibilities. However, 14% of respondents stated that gender has no bearing on how labor is divided. They were mixed waste segregators who gathered primary waste; all of them participated in the segregation process and were paid according to the weight of the waste they collected. The majority of the data shows the prevalence of gender disparities in work among male and female workers.

Men are allocated more physically demanding activities, like waste collection and loading/unloading, whereas women are primarily involved in waste segregation. The concept that men are more suited for labor-intensive jobs than women, as well as gender norms, establish this separation in duties and responsibilities. Women are also not allowed to work in jobs that require them to travel, like picking up waste from homes or navigating the streets. Additionally,

it was observed that women favored group work, which is similar to the Sapkota et al. (2020) study. This was because there was a chance that the male waste workers might harass and mock them. The safety of the waste workers is also called into question by these responses of female waste workers.

A female waste worker, over four years of experience, expressed interest in machine handling, but due to male dominance, females did not use baling operators. This demonstrates the limitations placed on women by sociocultural and occupational boundaries. They are forced to participate in collection and segregation rather than machine operation due to the safety dangers, harassment, and social stigma.

4.7.2 Specific Health Risks and Gender-Based Challenges in Work

Figure 4.18: Health Risks faced among male and female waste workers

All the waste workers, 47 male and 19 female workers, reported experiencing back pain or physical strain. This shows both of the groups experience severe strain due to physically demanding work-related health issues. Men are mostly assigned labor-intensive tasks, such as waste collection, lifting heavy waste, loading and unloading, and operating machines. This put immense pressure on their backs and joints. Likewise, women also suffer from physical strain due to prolonged standing, bending, and repetitive movements while collecting and segregating

waste, causing chronic pain and musculoskeletal issues. Both groups had a variety of health concerns, but the severity, nature, and intensity varied depending on their tasks.

Women who are involved in segregation are in direct and constant contact with the waste material. With no protective safety equipment available, such as gloves and proper sanitation, the higher risk of infection is increased. Men involved in traveling, such as cycle hawkers and door-to-door collectors, often travel longer hours with a heavier load of waste. Whereas, women's fatigue is linked with their dual responsibilities of managing household chores after work. Men majorly work in open areas where they are exposed to inhaling dust and polluted air, while women work in enclosed sorting areas with no proper ventilation. The presence of fine dust present in waste causes long-term respiratory damage while sorting dry plastic particles.

4.7.3 Availability of Basic Facilities

Figure 4.19: Availability of basic facilities for waste workers

The data indicates the inadequate availability of basic facilities in the workplace for waste workers. This has a direct impact on their well-being and efficiency. The 56 respondents responded with the availability of washroom facilities and drinking water. Door-to-door collectors do not have a designated space as they travel to different locations for waste collection. This condition leaves them with no access to basic facilities such as washrooms, drinking water, and changing rooms. The companies also avoid taking on responsibilities for

providing sanitary facilities. Similarly, cycle hawkers move across places all day, meaning they spend long hours cycling and collecting waste. Unlike the workers in scrap centers who have access to restrooms, IWWs with mobility roles are left to manage everything by themselves. This inadequate access to the basics leaves them with no alternatives but to find temporary solutions. Prolonged travel with no washroom discourages them from drinking water, which can lead to dehydration, kidney problems, or urinary infections.

The prevalence of washroom and drinking water for most workers is a positive sign. However, all workers raised concerns regarding hygiene and sanitation. Only 33 respondents have access to a changing room; this shows a lack of dedicated space for themselves after handling waste. Changing rooms are essential for waste workers, particularly due to the intensity of their work that involves waste, dirt, and unsanitary conditions. The female waste workers reported facing discomfort while changing work clothes before going home. Changing rooms also provide a space for workers short rest periods to take rest and cool down. The absence of such facilities challenges women, particularly during menstruation raising hygiene concerns. The lack of these basic sanitation facilities demonstrates how waste workers are disregarded.

4.7.4 Challenges Faced During Menstrual Cycles

Figure 4.20: Challenges faced by female waste workers during Menstrual Cycle

None of the female workers reported having access to menstruation health facilities at work. They complained about being forced to work despite their menstrual discomfort. Paid leave is not provided; however, the female segregators stated that they have the flexibility to not work, but it comes at the cost of their daily income. Women are compelled to work under uncomfortable and unhygienic conditions due to the lack of proper restrooms and changing facilities. Kunwar & Singh (2021) also confirmed women's health risks are affected by poor sanitation facilities and a lack of menstrual hygiene management. This shows a complete lack of support for female workers.

Without seating areas, continuous standing, lifting, and exposure to unsanitary waste create constant pain and exhaustion yet IWWs continue to work without any adjustments. This may increase the risk of urinary tract infections, skin diseases, and reproductive health issues. As the waste sector is frequently male-dominated, this may contribute to a lack of sensitivity, further excluding women. With no financial stability or health concerns, this indicates that women's participation is directly related to these aspects discouraging them from participating. Furthermore, the social stigma associated with menstruation hinders women from working in male-dominated settings. This demonstrates that fewer women only have access to enter or remain in the waste sector.

4.8 Contribution of IWWs in Plastic Waste Management

4.8.1 Daily Volume of Plastics Collected

Figure 4.21: Daily volume of plastic waste collected by various Informal Waste Workers

The data from the survey reveals that daily waste collection by waste workers, i.e., cycle hawkers and door-to-door collectors, focuses on moderate-scale waste collection from residential and commercial areas. Baling machine operators handle the largest volume of waste, accounting for over 100 kg per day. They are heavily involved in the bulk processing and handling of plastic waste sourced from various industries and scrap centers. Mixed waste segregators collect an average of 60-70 kg per day, with the highest estimated 80-90 kg of waste segregated during summer and the lowest 40-50 kg during winter. While recyclable segregators segregate 80–90 kg on average during summer and 50–60 kg in winter. This highlights the dual aspects of the market which varies seasonally and shows both inefficiencies and uncertainties in collecting waste.

Figure 4.22 : Overall Distribution of Volume of Plastic Waste Collected

This shows the overall distribution of daily plastic waste among 66 respondents. The largest volume of plastic waste falls within the category of 40–50 kg, covering 27% of the total collection. 50-60 kg and 60-70 kg and more than 100 kg each account for 17% each. And 80-90 kg of plastic waste collection accounts for 12%.

Both the findings show that the waste collection practices by the informal waste workers handle moderate volumes of waste, suggesting mid-sized collection is most commonly practiced. It is evident from the data that baling machine operators manage high volumes of waste—more than 100 kg per day. Their involvement in bulk processing and aggregation demonstrates how they manage substantial amounts of plastic waste ending up in landfills. They primarily handle the waste that is sourced from local aggregators, where the unaffiliated workers collect and sell their moderately collected waste daily. However, there is substantial variation in the study of the lower waste volume categories, such as the 20–30 kg and 30-40 kg categories. This implies that waste collection procedures are not homogeneous but depend on several external factors, including seasonal variation and market demand. Waste volumes increase during festival seasons or high commercial activities and decrease during off-seasons such as winter. Furthermore, the absence of reliable records of day-to-day waste collections may complicate the planning and resource allocation due to this unpredictability.

4.8.2 Types of Plastic Waste Collected Most Frequently

Figure 4.23: Common plastic waste collected by Informal Waste Workers

The data shows that HDPE (e.g., detergent containers) and PET (e.g., water bottles) is frequently collected, making up 46% and 45%, respectively. This shows that HDPE and PET are the most commonly used and discarded plastics, which are extensively used in household items, packaging, and beverage containers. LDPE (e.g., plastic bags) and PP (e.g., milk pouches) represent only 6% of the plastic waste collected by the IWWs. There is insufficient infrastructure for collecting this kind of plastic waste; thus, it is discarded in the environment improperly. Interview with scrap center owners confirmed that LDPE and PP are ignored due to their poor economic worth, higher operational cost and limited in recycling infrastructure.

The study reveals that different groups significantly influence the variation in plastic collection. Cycle hawkers and door-to-door collectors provide a steady flow of plastics into the recycling system from commercial and household wastes. HDPE and PET plastics are collected and segregated by mixed segregators and recyclable segregators. The baling machine operators collect a considerable amount of PET for processing and recycling. The plastic collection pattern shows a strong focus on PET and HDPE in the existing collection system. The high market value and their feasibility in recycling are the main drivers. On the other hand, the limited collection of lightweight plastics such as LDPE and PP creates a possible gap in waste collection

and recycling systems due to their low market value. According to IWWs, LDPE is lightweight, flexible, and frequently contaminated with oils and food residue, which makes collection more difficult. The overall collection patterns help us understand the significance of IWWs in collecting high-value plastics like PET and HDPE.

4.8.3 Types of Plastics Commonly Sent for Recycling

Figure 4.24: Types of plastics commonly sent for Recycling

Data shows that, at 48% and 44%, PET and HDPE, respectively, are mostly recycled plastics. Lightweight polymers like LDPE, on the other hand, are completely excluded from the recycling procedure. 8% of waste workers reported having no knowledge regarding plastics' potential for recycling. The lack of awareness highlights a significant gap among waste collectors regarding the recyclability of different plastics. The full absence of LDPE in recycling suggests no proper infrastructure, market limitations, and challenges in processing it due to its lower value.

The dominance of PET and HDPE in recycling efforts is due to their higher market value, rising demand, and greater recyclability. According to the interview with scrap center owners, PET and HDPE are easier to sort and recycle than other plastic varieties, such as LDPE, making them more appealing to both collectors and recyclers. PET and HDPE have local collection channels in the Terai region, ensuring a steady supply to recycling facilities. In contrast, LDPE is usually

melted and repurposed into black pipes; however, the demand for these types of plastics is low due to high transportation costs and less economic return.

4.8.4 Distribution Channels for Plastic Waste for Recycling

Figure 4.25: Distribution Channels for Plastic Waste Recycling

From the data, 50% of the plastics are sold to scrap traders/aggregators, while 37% are sold to recycling facilities. 13% of the respondents were unaware of the distribution of collected plastics for recycling. The local scrap centers purchased the collected plastics from the majority of unaffiliated waste workers. On the other hand, the high-scale scrap center purchased the separated plastics from the low-scale local scrap centers. After being baled into bale boxes, these plastics are delivered to the recycling facilities, where they are converted into secondary raw materials.

Half of plastics are sold to local aggregators and traders, indicating that these intermediaries facilitate waste collection through an informal channel. Informal waste workers preferably sell their collected recyclables at low profit margins to such intermediaries due to easy access and immediate payment. The scrap center owner directly deals with the recyclable facilities without the involvement of the workers. This shows the high barriers to access to recycling facilities by marginalized groups. There is hierarchy in plastic waste management where a major portion of plastic waste is managed by the local centers and recycling facilities, with IWWs occupying the lowest tier in the system.

Chapter 5: Conclusion

Growing urbanization and consumer demand cause plastic waste to steadily increase, causing a direct impact on the environment. Informal waste workers are the primary suppliers of raw materials for the recycling industry. Through their efforts, plastics collected from households, businesses, and streets are sent to scrap centers, which are processed and forwarded to recycling facilities. Thus, IWWs are crucial for maintaining the local economy and lowering plastic pollution.

The findings indicate that different types of informal waste workers, i.e., cycle hawkers, door-to-door collectors, mixed waste segregators, recyclable segregators, and baling machine operators, are responsible for waste management from collection to recycling. However, they have limited access to training programs, skill development, or financial security measures. The exposure to occupational health risks makes IWWs vulnerable, especially women during the menstrual cycle, due to inadequate sanitation facilities in workplaces. Most IWWs are uninformed of or lack access to insurance programs that could protect them from accidents, illness, and financial hardship.

Every day, LMC produces 96 tons of plastic waste, necessitating efficient waste management. On average, each worker collects and processes 60–70 kilograms of plastic waste daily. The combined effort of just twenty waste workers might result in the recovery of more than one ton of plastic waste per day. Given that thousands of unregistered waste workers operate in LMC, their collective contribution plays a direct impact in reducing unmanaged plastic waste and supporting the circular economy. If informal waste workers recover even 10% of LMC's daily plastic waste, they could substantially alleviate the burden on landfills and municipal waste disposal systems.

Although, scrap center generates a significant revenue—estimated at NPR 55.6 million per month in Kathmandu Valley—the condition of IWWs continues to remain poor. Despite IWWs working at the forefront in recovery and recycling process, they receive minimal benefits and face harsh working conditions. This shows a clear hierarchy among the waste management

sector where those at the bottom—IWWs, are the one who suffers the most with no legal support, fair compensation and protection.

The demolition of scrap centers in Kathmandu Metropolitan City is a clear indication of systematic negligence and the vulnerability of informal waste workers. As these initiatives are taking place in the urban cities of Nepal, there is a high probability of similar actions being implemented in LMC. As a result, they might face policy-driven displacement, economic instability, and a lack of formal protection. The demolition of the scrap center further pushes IWWs into uncertainty, forcing them to relocate, work in unsafe environments, or lose their only source of income.

By optimizing waste collection and processing systems, LMC can transition towards a more sustainable circular economy, where waste is minimized and materials are continuously reused. However, this would not be possible without integrating informal waste workers into formal frameworks. Legal recognition, social security, and access to training programs would improve not only their status but also strengthen the circular economy capabilities of LMC.

Chapter 6: Recommendations

Based on a survey of informal waste workers, interview with scrap center owners, and KII with LMC Environmental Chief Officer, the following recommendations can improve the overall status of informal waste workers and improve their working conditions, safety, as well as recyclable waste recovery efforts, thereby promoting a circular economy.

- The government should allocate designated spaces for the regulation of scrap centers for its smooth operations. The municipal authorities must enforce safety guidelines and operational requirements, with regular monitoring of scrap centers to ensure compliance and proper working conditions for the workers.
- The government should invest in waste-to-money initiatives, promoting recycling and resource recovery. By integrating waste management into the circular economy, discarded materials can be reused, recycled, and repurposed, that not only reduces landfill waste but also generates economic opportunities
- Waste workers are either unaware or ignorant of basic health care and services available to them. Training and awareness programs should be implemented by government to educate them on occupational health hazards, safety precautions, and access to medical services, assuring their well-being and protection.
- There should be provisions for the issuance of ID cards and a uniform dress code for informal waste workers that acknowledge their work, promote societal acceptance, and ensure easy access to waste collection without discrimination.
- Every informal waste worker should be entitled to a social safety net such as the Social Security Fund (SSF), which includes health insurance, accident insurance, and financial assistance in times of need. These entitlements protect workers from insecure wages and hazardous working conditions and ensure their long-term dignity.

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Appendices

Appendix I: Structured Questionnaire for IWWS

Name of the Respondent:

Age:

Gender:

Marital Status:

Education Level:

1. How long have you been working in the waste management sector?
2. What is your primary role in plastic waste management?
3. What is your average monthly income from this work? Or is this based on the amount of plastic you recycle?
4. How many hours do you work daily?
5. How regular is your income from waste collection?
6. Do you have any additional sources of income?
7. Do your working conditions impact your health or work? If yes, how?
8. Do you have access to health services? If yes, are they affordable and accessible?
9. Do you have access to banking or savings services? If yes, have you ever taken loans for equipment, health, or housing?
10. Are you employed on a contract basis, or do you work independently?
11. Do you have access to safety equipment? If yes, how often is the equipment replaced or maintained?
12. Have you received training on safety protocols (e.g., handling hazardous waste, injury prevention)?
13. What are the most common hazards you face during work? And If injured, how do you usually manage treatment?
14. How would you describe your job security?
 Very Secure

- Secure
 - Somewhat Secure
 - Insecure
 - Looking for another option
15. Are you aware of any health or accidental insurance or policies at work? And do you currently have accidental or health insurance coverage?
 16. What kind of support would you like to reduce risks and improve safety in your work?
 17. Do you believe your role or responsibilities in waste collection are affected by your gender? If yes, please elaborate
 18. Are there any specific physical challenges in your role that you find difficult?
 19. And what types of health risks do you associate with your tasks?
 20. Do you think there is a difference in pay between male and female workers in your field?
 21. Is there a place for managing menstrual health at work (e.g., restrooms, disposal areas)?
 22. What challenges do you face working during your menstrual cycle?
 23. How much plastic waste do you collect daily?
 - Less than 10 kg
 - 10-20 kg
 - 21-50 kg
 - More than 50 kg (please specify): _____
 24. Which type of plastic waste do you collect the most? What percentage of the collected plastic waste is recycled, and what percentage is sent to landfills?
 25. What types of plastics are mostly sent for recycling?
 26. What happens to the plastic waste you collect?
 27. What kind of support from authorities or organizations would help improve waste management processes?

Appendix II: Interview of Scrap Center Owner

1. How long has your scrap center been operating? Is it officially registered?
2. How many workers are employed at your center? Are they employed full-time, part-time, or on a contract basis?
3. What is the average wage offered to workers? Do wages vary depending on gender and skills?
4. What steps have been taken for the safety of the workers? Do you ensure occupational health and safety protocols at your center?
5. Do you provide accidental or health insurance for your workers? If yes, how is it facilitated?
6. What are the daily volumes (in kilograms) of plastic waste collected, processed, or sent to recycling facilities?
7. Which type of plastic waste do you collect the most? And what amount (kg) of the collected plastic waste is recycled and sent to landfills?
8. Where do you usually send the collected plastic waste for recycling? Who are your main buyers or customers for processed plastic waste?
9. Are there legal, environmental, or social barriers limiting your operations?
10. Have you received any financial or policy support (e.g., grants, subsidies, or incentives) from the government or NGOs?

Appendix III: Key Informant Interview of LMC Official

1. Can you explain the current waste management system in Lalitpur Metropolitan City?
2. What are the main challenges Lalitpur Metropolitan City faces in managing waste effectively?
3. Are there any policies, plans, or strategies specifically targeting plastic waste management in Lalitpur?
4. How would you describe the role of informal waste workers (IWWs) in the plastic waste management system?
5. Are there any programs, training, or support systems in place for informal waste workers?
6. As KMC is planning to implement a tender system, what are the possibilities of implementing similar regulations in LMC?
7. If this is implemented, waste management will become more regulated. However, many waste workers rely on the centers for their livelihood. What are your thoughts on this?
8. What future plans or strategies are in place for improving plastic waste management in Lalitpur?
9. Are there any plans to formalize the role of informal waste workers or integrate them into the municipal waste management system?
10. What suggestions would you think would be to improve the effectiveness of waste management in Lalitpur?

Appendix IV: Thematic Categorization of Job Security of Informal Waste Workers

Themes	Key Responses	Key Insights
Dependency on Daily Income	Our only source of income is the waste collected in a day; during COVID, we couldn't afford food and had to return to Bihar."	Informal Waste Worker's wages directly depend on the recyclables and any disruption leads to financial instability
Vulnerability to External Factors	"We are paid daily; if we are sick or the center shuts down, we don't get paid." "On days when it rains heavily, there are fewer chances for us to work, and recently the flood affected our income."	Any health issues or weather conditions have a direct linkage to their earnings
Work Uncertainty	"Sometimes, even if we travel all day, we don't get any waste from households, leading to no payment that day." "Working in this sector is very unstable; some days there is constant work, and some days there is no work at all." "Working in this sector is very unstable; some days there is constant work, and some days there is no work at all."	The income of workers is volatile due to external factors and is highly unpredictable

Additional Income Source	"I have a pig farm at Pharping; I take the organic waste as food for my pigs. This saves my money as well as providing additional income."	Wastes as a secondary source of income to supplement their earnings from waste collection
	"After collecting wastes from households, we segregate wastes and sell them in local scrap centers before sending it to landfills."	

Table 8: Categorization of Job Security of Informal Waste Workers